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Plagiarism in Scientific Writing

Shivakumar Acharya,

*Asst Librarian-BLDE (Deemed to be
University),
Shri. B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital &
Research Centre, Vijayapura,
shivakumar.15august@gmail.com;*

Dr. K. Shanmukhappa,

*Assistant Librarian, University Library,
Bangalore University, Bengaluru,
shanmukhappa.k@gmail.com*

Abstract:

Plagiarism is getting increasingly common across all industries. Plagiarism is a serious problem that the majority of writers are unaware of. Plagiarism can range from basic deception to a more serious issue where authors cut-copy-paste from the original material without correctly acknowledging the main source. When we use databases such as LISA/Google Scholar/MedLine/Pubmed, we find a wealth of material on plagiarism. Knowing how to avoid plagiarism, on the other hand, remains a matter of interest for all researchers. It is now the responsibility of every young researcher to be aware of ethical standards when writing scientific articles. If we apply our own ideas, we can write the paper totally without consulting the original source.

Introduction:

Plagiarism comes from the Latin word “plagium”, which means "to kidnap a man." It's a literary term for stealing someone else's work and presenting it as their own.(7)

Plagiarism is the theft of intellectual or literary property (intentional or unintentional). Plagiarism occurs when someone, without their permission, uses another person's language, ideas, or any other type of text, figure, or graph that is not part of common original knowledge.

“According to the Merriam-Webster online dictionary, to "plagiarize" means:

- “to steal and pass off (the ideas or words of another) as one's own”
- “to use (another's production) without crediting the source”
- “to commit literary theft”
- “to present as new and original an idea or product derived from an existing source” (8)

Understanding plagiarism, its varieties, and the consequences of plagiarism is critical for students, teachers, and academicians. Plagiarism has always existed, but students now have a greater number of techniques to plagiarise without being caught. It is now quite simple allowing a student to just take material and use it in part or in its entirety in their own work that is something we must acknowledge. plagiarism is not tolerated in academic writing, and that stealing someone else's work is a criminal offence. It's also important to realise that plagiarism has major ramifications. If you are a faculty member, you may be fired or demoted from your position, you will also be barred from supervising PhD students. Furthermore, if you are a student, it is possible that your registration as a PhD student will be revoked. (4)

Researchers and authors of academic papers must adhere to Good Scientific Practice guidelines. Honesty and integrity are two principles that should be followed. In today's collaborative world, in addition to trans-disciplinary research every author's honesty is important becoming a pillar of science that can be trusted (3)

Reasons for Plagiarism:

There are a variety of reasons why a teacher or a student plagiarises. A teacher may plagiarise in order to get an unfair advantage in publishing/writing projects/books, for example. However, there are a variety of reasons why a student plagiarises. Let's look at why a student plagiarises in their writing.

Study Pressure

This is one of the reasons why students plagiarise in academic work. Students are busy with a number of duties, including assignments, presentations, and term end examinations, in addition to needing to write their synopsis/papers, thus it's conceivable that this is one of the reasons they find cutting, copying, and pasting so straightforward. (4)

Disorganized

When you're unorganised, you're constantly thinking about what you should do, what you shouldn't do, and what you should do first. What I'm going to do after that... In the meanwhile, you might just copy from the internet or another source.(4)

Poor Study Habits

When students are uninterested in their research or job. They just shrug it off and try to find any easy method to finish their project or whatever work they've been given. (4)

English as a foreign language

Students who are not native English speakers may find it difficult to write in English. (4)

Lack of strict academic discipline

Students and even teachers are frequently unaware of the consequences of plagiarism due to a lack of awareness of the implications. It may result in plagiarism in rare cases. (4)

Types of Plagiarism:

Plagiarism can be classified in four different ways.

Direct Plagiarism:-When a paragraph is copied word for word without quote marks or attribution, this is known as direct plagiarism. That is, passing it off as his or her own work, in whole or in part, without acknowledgement constitutes direct plagiarism. Plagiarism is unethical and academic misconduct, and it can lead to disciplinary action if found. The consequences of plagiarism can be quite hazardous.

Mosaic Plagiarism (Patch writing):-Mosaic Plagiarism is defined as stealing terms from any source without putting quote marks around them, or attempting to find synonyms for the author's language while keeping the text's fundamental meaning intact. Patch writing is another name for it. Whether done intentionally or unwittingly, this form of paraphrasing is considered academic misconduct. Even if you cite your source in the footnotes, it's still unlawful.

Self-Plagiarism:-Self-plagiarism occurs when a student reuses or combines elements of his or her own earlier work without the permission of all co-authors involved.

Self-plagiarism, for example, occurs when you incorporate a portion of a paper written at the graduate level into a paper you will write after graduation. Self-plagiarism is when you take advantage of one piece of work over and over again... It's the equivalent of utilising one research paper for two degrees, or not being able to copy figures, tables, or text from a previous publication into a new manuscript.

In theory, you must obtain permission before repeating the content.... otherwise; it will be considered self-plagiarism.

Accidental Plagiarism:-When you're working on a piece of literature, you may inadvertently plagiarise. You simply fail to cite your sources, misquote them, or mistakenly paraphrase them by using comparable words or groupings of words without attribution. Students should learn how to reference and keep meticulous records of the sources they've used (should develop note taking habit). It indicates that you should be meticulous in recording down even the smallest details. For example, if you have taken a few lines from a book and the book is misplaced, there may be an issue with referring, which you might have prevented if you had written the book's reference beforehand.(4)

UGC about Plagiarism:

Regulations of the University Grants Commission (Promotion of Academic Integrity and Plagiarism Prevention in Higher Educational Institutions), 2018. These rules will apply to all students, instructors, researchers, and employees of the country's higher education institutions. These regulations become effective on the 23rd of July, 2018, when they were published in the Official Gazette.

In this regulation it has given definitions to some technical words as follows:

“Plagiarism” means the practice of taking someone else’s work or idea and passing them as one’s own;

"Academic Integrity" refers to the intellectual honesty with which one proposes, performs, and reports any action that results in intellectual property production.

“Author” A student, faculty member, researcher, or staff member of a Higher Educational Institution (HEI) who claims to be the inventor of the work under review is referred to as a "author."

"Information" Data, message, text, images, sound, voice, codes, computer programmes, software, and databases, as well as microfilm or computer generated microfiche;

“Researcher” refers to a person who conducts academic or scientific research in higher education institutions;

“Staff” refers to all non-teaching employees who work in higher education institutions in whatever capacity, including regular, temporary, contract, outsourced, and so on.;

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“Student” denotes a student who has been accepted and is enrolled in a programme of study, including a research programme, in any form of study (full time or part-time or distance mode) ;(5)

UGC Guidelines for Curbing Plagiarism in HEI (Higher Education Institutions):

When theses, dissertations, publications, and other comparable materials are submitted, HEI must declare and implement a technology-based strategy that uses relevant instruments to ensure that they are free of plagiarism.

The technique mentioned above must be available to all study participants, including students, academics, researchers, and staff.

Every student who submits a thesis, dissertation, or other similar paper to the HEI must sign an undertaking stating that the document was written by him or her, that it is his or her original work, and that it is free of plagiarism.

The assurance must state that the document has been thoroughly examined using a Plagiarism Detection Tool that has been approved by the HEI.

The HEI will draught a plagiarism policy and get it authorised by the appropriate legislative bodies/authorities. The approved policy must be posted on the HEI website's homepage.

Each supervisor must submit a certificate stating that the work completed by the researcher under his or her supervision is free of plagiarism.

HEI will deliver soft copies of all Masters, Research programme dissertations, and thesis to INFLIBNET for hosting in the digital repository under the "Shodh Ganga e-repository" within a month of the award of degrees.

On the institute website, HEI will build an Institutional Repository that will store dissertations, theses, papers, publications, and other in-house publications.(5)

UGC Guidelines on Penalties:

Only after academic misconduct on the part of the individual has been proven beyond a reasonable doubt, after all avenues of appeal have been exhausted, and the individual in question has been given a fair and transparent opportunity to defend himself or herself, will penalties for plagiarism be imposed on students pursuing Masters and Research programmes, as well as researchers, faculty, and staff of the HEI. In case of plagiarism in academic and research publications

- I. Level 0: Similarities up to 10% - Minor similarities, no penalty.

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- II. Level 1: Similarities above 10% to 40%
 - i) Shall be asked to withdraw manuscript.
- III. Level 2: Similarities above 40% to 60%
 - i) Shall be asked to withdraw manuscript.
 - ii) Shall be denied a right to one annual increment.
 - iii) Shall not be allowed to be a supervisor to any new Master’s, M.Phil., Ph.D. Student/scholar for a period of two years.
- IV. Level 3: Similarities above 60%
 - i) Shall be asked to withdraw manuscript.
 - ii) Shall be denied a right to two successive annual increments.
 - iii) Shall not be allowed to be a supervisor to any new Master’s, M.Phil., Ph.D. Student/scholar for a period of three years.

UGC also has given another set of rules of penalties in case of plagiarism in submission of thesis and dissertations

Level 0: Similarities up to 10% - Minor Similarities, no penalty.

- ii. Level 1: Similarities above 10% to 40% - Such student shall be asked to submit a revised script within a stipulated time period not exceeding 6 months.
- iii. Level 2: Similarities above 40% to 60% - Such student shall be debarred from submitting a revised script for a period of one year.
- iv. Level 3: Similarities above 60% -Such student registration for that programme shall be cancelled.

Similarity checks for exclusion from Plagiarism

The research work done by students, instructors, researchers, and staff must be original, with abstracts, summaries, hypotheses, observations, results, conclusions, and recommendations being the only things that are comparable. It must not contain any common knowledge or coincidental terms for a period of up to fourteen (14) words. The UGC also suggest to exclude the following text while running the plagiarism

- i. All quoted work reproduced with all necessary permission and/or attribution.

- ii. All references, bibliography, table of content, preface and acknowledgements.
- iii. All generic terms, laws, standard symbols and standards equations.(5)

Plagiarism and its consequences:

Academic Penalties-Students that submit plagiarised work may face severe consequences, as previously indicated. Grade penalties, failure in a class or course, suspension, expulsion, or other disciplinary consequences, such as being excluded from extracurricular activities or sports, are all options. In some cases, students may be barred from attending other institutions or universities..

Loss of Creativity-Your creativity will suffer as a result of not pushing ourselves to develop unique content and new ideas. It's difficult to train your creative muscles when you're simply copying someone else's work. To make their work stand out, the finest writers push themselves to be more creative. Plagiarism prevents you from attempting to create something truly unique.

Damage to Reputation-Plagiarism can harm your personal and professional reputation in addition to harming your job. You may potentially endanger the brand you represent or your employer's reputation.

Dishearten the Followers/Audience- Followers of your work (students, staff) etc. feel dishearten of you plagiarized work and you lose your credibility among them.

Legal and Criminal Action: Finally, one of the most serious consequences of plagiarism is the risk of being sued or perhaps going to prison. Although most plagiarism matters are resolved without going to court, if the plagiarised content is protected by copyright law, you may be subject to legal fines or penalties. At the very least, you could be served with a cease and desist notice. (6)

Plagiarism Consequences Case Study-

A doctoral thesis rejected on charge of Plagiarism” (20 May, 2012)

“The University of Madras has rejected a research scholar's doctoral thesis on charges of plagiarism and has banned the student from re-registering for the degree at the university”.

A former university vice chancellor has been accused of plagiarism” (February 25, 2015)

“Former Delhi University vice chancellor Deepak Pental was arrested and sent to Tihar jail on Tuesday after a fellow professor complained of plagiarism and

illegally using a chemical substance from the university's science lab. Professor P Parthasarthy, had accused Pental of plagiarizing his paper on biotechnology”.(4)

How to avoid Plagiarism in Scientific Publications:

Plagiarism is when you purposefully or inadvertently pass off someone else's work as your own. This could include plagiarising or paraphrasing someone else's published or unpublished work without attribution, or misrepresenting someone else's artistic or technical work or production as your own.

Every HEI should implement the mechanism in order to raise awareness about responsible behaviour. Conducting research and academic activities in order to maintain academic integrity and avoid plagiarism.

HEI will teach students, teachers, researchers, and staff on correct attribution, obtaining author permission where necessary, and acknowledging sources in accordance with the needs and specificities of disciplines, as well as rules, international agreements, and regulations that regulate the source.

Every semester, HEI will hold seminars/awareness programmes for students, instructors, researchers, and staff on responsible research, thesis, and dissertation writing, as well as the promotion of academic integrity and ethics in education.

- i. Include the cardinal principles of academic integrity as a required course work/module in the curriculum of undergraduate (UG), postgraduate (PG), and master's degree programmes, among others.
- ii. Make components of responsible research conduct and publication ethics a required course. Master's and Research Scholars' work/module.
- iii. Incorporate components of responsible research conduct and publication ethics into Orientation and Instruction.
- iv. The HEI should organise refresher courses for its academics and personnel.
- v. Educate students, instructors, researchers, and staff on how to use plagiarism detection software and reference management tools.
- vi. Create a facility that is equipped with cutting-edge plagiarism detecting technology.
- vii. Encourage students, academics, researchers, and staff to join the International Registry of Researchers. (5)

Conclusion:

We must do more than preach about the advantages of academic integrity and condemn the immorality of taking other people's ideas to effectively combat plagiarism. We must concentrate our efforts on forming communities of practice that value creative and reflective writing. Students must participate in instruction that explains the origins and significance of intellectual honesty. Because of the current emphasis on testing and grades, instructors and students have lost sight of the more fundamental aims of education, such as lifelong learning and national and global citizenship. Students can be persuaded that plagiarism and other forms of academic dishonesty are not in their long-term best interests by refocusing on higher-order goals. Monitoring, promotion, and research development divisions should be developed in scientific and academic institutions. Plagiarism should not be excluded from exposure and consequences in science.

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